

Multiple vacation finite source queues with accessible batch service and with single departure

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Abstract

In this article, single server finite source queue is considered. The services are given in batches of variable size of maximum size M . If there are l ($1 < l < M$) customers at a service completion point, the remaining customers $M-l$ allowed to enter into the service batch. The source size is N . At a service completion point, if there are no customers in the waiting line, then the server leaves for vacation of multiple type. Two models are considered. One with infinite waiting line and the other with finite waiting line of size L . The transient solution to the models is obtained. Some performance measures are calculated. Control chart analysis is carried out. Some numerical illustrations are provided.

Index terms: Finite Source Queue-Single Departure-Batch Service-Accessible Batch-Transient Analysis-Performance Measures-Control chart analysis.

AMS 2000 Subject Classifications Number: 60K25, 60K30 and 90B22.

1 Introduction

Bulk queue is one of the fertile areas in queueing theory. The bulk queue of the arrival may be in batches and/or the service may be in batches. Bailey (1954) considered a bulk queue in which units are served in batches not more than b . Neuts (1967) considered a batch service rule called bulk service rule. The rule with a fixed batch size K has been considered by Fabens (1961), Bhat (1963) considered a rule in which the batch size is a random variable.

Kleinrock (1975) considered the finite source model $M/M/c//m$. An application of the model $M/M/N//N$ in electronics is considered by Koenigsberg (1980). The $M/G/1//N$ system, sometimes called machine interference problem (Saaty (1961)) is analyzed in detail by Takacs (1962). Jaiswal (1968), Cooper (1981), Stecke (1982), Stecke and Aronson (1985) and Bunday (1986). Some other notable works in this area are Papadopoulos and Heavey (1996), Syski (1997), Ching (2001), Chakravarthy and Agarwal (2003) and Aliakbar Montazer Haghighi and Dimitar Mishav (2007).

In real life, there may be situations, where as soon as the server becomes free, the server shut down the service facility temporarily for a random period of time and thus the server may not be available when the customer arrives to an empty queue, the service starts only after the server returns to the queue. This random period is called vacation period and the queue is called

a vacation queue. Miller (1964), first studied a model, where the server is unavailable for service during some random length of time for the $M/G/1$ queueing system. The term vacation was first used by Cooper (1970). Various modifications have been defined on the number of vacation periods and the time points at which the vacation starts or ends. Some modifications are compulsory vacation policy, Bernoulli vacation policy, single vacation policy and multiple vacation policy.

In many real situations, it can be seen that the server works during his rest period, called working vacation, but with slower rate (most frequently). In recent years, many researchers working on the queueing system with server working vacation. These queues have applications in the field of telecommunication and manufacturing systems. Some notable works in this area are Servi and Finn (2002), Kim et al. (2003), Wu and Takagi (2006), Liu et al. (2007) and Xu et al. (2009). Lin et al. (2008) consider a multi-server queue with single working vacation. Jain and Jain (2010) investigated a single working vacation model with breakdown. Ke et al. (2010) have given a short survey on vacation models in recent years. Kalyanaraman and Sundaramoorthy (2018), analyzed a single server working vacation queue with server state dependent arrival rates.

The model analyzed in this article contains a source of size N . The customer arrival follows Poisson process. Service time is exponentially distributed. Services are given in batches of maximum size M with accessible type. At the service completion point, the server takes multiple vacation.

2 The Model

The arrivals are from a source of size N . Arrival occurs according to a Poisson process with rate λ . Service times are exponentially distributed with state dependent parameter. i.e., depends on number of customers undergoing service. The services are given in batches of variable size j ($1 \leq j \leq M$). The maximum number of customers in the service station at a time is M ($< N$). The service batches are accessible batches.

At the time of arrival if the number of customers in the service station is less than M , then the arrival joins the service batch. In the waiting line, the first in first out (FIFO) queue discipline is used. The services are given in batches but the customers depart singly after completing service. At a service completion point, if there are no customers in the queue, the server leaves for a vacation. The vacation period follows negative exponential with rate θ . After completion, if there are no customers in the queue the server takes another vacation this continues at least one customer in the queue (Multiple vacation). Two models are defined and analyzed in transient state. For the analysis, the following notations have been introduced: Let, $X(t)$ be number in the Queue at time t , $X(t) \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, N - M\}$, $Y(t)$ be number in the service station at time t , $Y(t) \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, M\}$ and $Z(t)$ be the server state, $Z(t) \in \{0, 1\}$, $Z(t) = 0$, the server is on vacation at time t and $Z(t) = 1$, the server is busy at time t . The stochastic process $\{(X(t), Y(t), Z(t)): t \geq 0\}$ is a Markov Process. The first model (Model I) is the delay model and the second model (Model II) is the loss model. These models are analyzed in section 3 and 4. A comparative numerical study is given in section 5.

3 Model-I and Analysis

$p'_{(0,M)}(t) = -[(N - M)\lambda + M\mu_M]p_{(0,M)}(t) + (N - M + 1)\lambda p_{(0,M-1)}(t)$ In addition to the model definition in section 2, the waiting line capacity is assumed to be infinite, called delay model. In subsection 3.1, a transient analysis is presented and performance measures are presented in the subsection 3.2.

3.1 Transient Analysis

The state space is $S = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, N - M\} \times \{0, 1, 2, \dots, M\} \times \{0, 1\}$ and let $p_{(n, m)}(t) = Pr\{X(t) = n, Y(t) = m, Z(t) = 1\}$, $q_{(n, m)}(t) = Pr\{X(t) = n, Y(t) = m, Z(t) = 0\}$ be the probability distributions when the server is busy and the server is on vacation respectively.

The forward Kolmogorov equations of the process are obtained as,

$$q'_{(0,0)}(t) = -N\lambda q_{(0,0)}(t) + \mu_1 p_{(0,1)}(t) \tag{3.1}$$

$$p'_{(0,1)}(t) = -[(N - 1)\lambda + \mu_1]p_{(0,1)}(t) + 2\mu_2 p_{(0,2)}(t) + \theta q_{(0,1)}(t) \tag{3.2}$$

$$p'_{(0,n)}(t) = -[(N - n)\lambda + n\mu_n]p_{(0,n)}(t) + (N - n + 1)\lambda p_{(0,n-1)}(t) + (n + 1)\mu_{n+1}p_{(0,n+1)}(t) + \theta q_{(0,n)}(t); \quad 2 \leq n \leq M - 1 \tag{3.3}$$

$$p'_{(0,M)}(t) = -[(N - M)\lambda + M\mu_M]p_{(0,M)}(t) + (N - M + 1)\lambda p_{(0,M-1)}(t) + M\mu_M p_{(1,M)}(t) + \theta q_{(0,M)}(t) \tag{3.4}$$

$$p'_{(n,M)}(t) = -[(N - M - n)\lambda + M\mu_M]p_{(n,M)}(t) + (N - M - n + 1)\lambda p_{(n-1,M)}(t) + M\mu_M p_{(n+1,M)}(t) + \theta q_{(n,M)}(t); \quad 1 \leq n \leq N - M - 1 \tag{3.5}$$

$$p'_{(N-M,M)}(t) = -M\mu_M p_{(N-M,M)}(t) + \lambda p_{(N-M-1,M)}(t) + \theta q_{(N-M,M)}(t) \tag{3.6}$$

$$q'_{(0,n)}(t) = -[(N - n)\lambda + \theta]q_{(0,n)}(t) + (N - n + 1)\lambda q_{(0,n-1)}(t); \quad 1 \leq n \leq M \tag{3.7}$$

$$q'_{(n,M)}(t) = -[(N - (M + n))\lambda + \theta]q_{(n,M)}(t) + (N - (M + n - 1))\lambda q_{(n-1,M)}(t); \quad 1 \leq n \leq N - M \tag{3.8}$$

The corresponding matrix form for equations (3.1) to (3.8) is,

$$p'(t) = Ap(t) \tag{3.9}$$

where,

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} D_0 & B_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ D_1 & A_1 & B_2 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & C_1 & A_2 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C_2 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & A_{M-1} & B_M & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & C_{M-1} & A_M & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & A_{M+(N-M-1)} & B_{M+(N-M)} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & C_{M+(N-M-1)} & A_{M+(N-M)} \end{bmatrix}$$

and the submatrices are

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_0 &= [-N\lambda], D_1 = \begin{bmatrix} N\lambda \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, B_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \mu_1 \end{bmatrix} \\
 B_i &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & i\mu_i \end{bmatrix}; \quad 2 \leq i \leq M \\
 B_{M+i} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & M\mu_M \end{bmatrix}; \quad 1 \leq i \leq N-M \\
 C_i &= \begin{bmatrix} (N-i)\lambda & 0 \\ 0 & (N-i)\lambda \end{bmatrix}; \quad 1 \leq i \leq M \\
 C_{M+i} &= \begin{bmatrix} (N-(M+i)\lambda & 0 \\ 0 & (N-(M+i)\lambda) \end{bmatrix}; \quad 1 \leq i \leq N-M-1 \\
 A_i &= \begin{bmatrix} -[(N-i)\lambda + \theta] & 0 \\ \theta & -[(N-i)\lambda + i\mu_i] \end{bmatrix}; \quad 1 \leq i \leq M \\
 A_{M+i} &= \begin{bmatrix} -[(N-(M+i)\lambda + \theta] & 0 \\ \theta & -[(N-(M+i)\lambda + M\mu_M] \end{bmatrix}; \quad 1 \leq i \leq N-M
 \end{aligned}$$

Let the probability distribution be,

$$p(t) = (p_0(t), p_1(t), \dots, p_{M-1}(t), p_M(t), p_{M+1}(t), \dots, p_{M+(N-M-1)}(t), p_{M+(N-M)}(t))^T \tag{3.10}$$

where,

$$p_0(t) = (q_{(0,0)}(t))$$

$$p_i(t) = (q_{(0,i)}(t), p_{(0,i)}(t)); \quad 1 \leq i \leq M$$

$$p_{M+i}(t) = (q_{(i,M)}(t), p_{(i,M)}(t)); \quad 1 \leq i \leq N-M$$

Integrating the equation (3.9), we get,

$$p(t) = e^{At}.C \tag{3.11}$$

$$\text{At } t=0, C=p(0) \tag{3.12}$$

$$\text{The solution vector at time } t \text{ is, } p(t) = p(0).e^{At} \tag{3.13}$$

where $p(0)$ is the initial probability vector.

The exponential of the matrix can be computed in many ways (Moler and Loan (2003)). The methods can be obtained from classical results in analysis, approximation theory and matrix theory. One of the methods is the series method. An algorithm is developed, the definition $e^{At} = I + At + \frac{(At)^2}{2!} + \dots$ is the basis for the algorithm. The series is summed until adding another term does not alter the recent number stored in the computer. Then the resulting value is taken as e^{At} . The probability vector $p(t)$ in (3.13) is obtained by assuming the initial probability vector $p(0) = [1, 0, 0, \dots, 0]^T$.

3.2 Some Performance Measures

By straight forward calculation, the following performances are obtained.

1. Mean number of customers in the queue at time t

$$L_1(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-M} n[q_{(n,M)}(t) + p_{(n,M)}(t)] \quad (3.14)$$

2. Mean number of customers in the system at time t

$$L_2(t) = \sum_{n=0}^M n[q_{(0,n)}(t) + p_{(0,n)}(t)] + \sum_{n=0}^{N-M} n[q_{(n,M)}(t) + p_{(n,M)}(t)] \quad (3.15)$$

3. Mean number of customers in the system at time t

$$L_3(t) = \sum_{n=0}^M n^2[q_{(0,n)}(t) + p_{(0,n)}(t)] + \sum_{n=0}^{N-M} n^2[q_{(n,M)}(t) + p_{(n,M)}(t)] \quad (3.16)$$

4. Mean number of customers in the service station at time t

$$L_4(t) = \sum_{n=0}^M n[p_{(0,n)}(t) + q_{(0,n)}(t)] + M \sum_{n=1}^{N-M} [p_{(n,M)}(t) + q_{(n,M)}(t)] \quad (3.17)$$

5. Mean number of customers in the source at time t

$$L_5(t) = \sum_{n=0}^M (N - n)[q_{(0,n)}(t) + p_{(0,n)}(t)] + \sum_{n=1}^{N-M} (N - M - n)[q_{(n,M)}(t) + p_{(n,M)}(t)] \quad (3.18)$$

6. Mean number of customers in the queue when the server is on vacation at time t

$$L_6(t) = \sum_{n=0}^M nq_{(0,n)}(t) + \sum_{n=0}^{N-M} nq_{(n,M)}(t) \quad (3.19)$$

7. Mean number of customers in the system when the server is busy

$$L_7(t) = \sum_{n=0}^M np_{(0,n)}(t) + \sum_{n=1}^{N-M} (n + M)p_{(n,M)}(t) \quad (3.20)$$

4 Model-II and Analysis

In this model, the waiting line capacity is taken as L . If the waiting line is full, the arriving customers leave the system. This model is called the Loss model.

4.1 Transient Analysis

The state space is $S = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, L\} \times \{0, 1, 2, \dots, M\} \times \{0, 1\}$ and let $p_{(n, m)}(t) = Pr\{X(t) = n, Y(t) = m, Z(t) = 1\}$, $q_{(n, m)}(t) = Pr\{X(t) = n, Y(t) = m, Z(t) = 0\}$ be the probability distributions when the server is busy and the server is on vacation respectively.

The forward Kolmogorov equations of the process are obtained as,

$$q'_{(0,0)}(t) = -N\lambda q_{(0,0)}(t) + \mu_1 p_{(0,1)}(t) \quad (4.1)$$

$$p'_{(0,1)}(t) = -[(N-1)\lambda + \mu_1]p_{(0,1)}(t) + 2\mu_2 p_{(0,2)}(t) + \theta q_{(0,1)}(t) \tag{4.2}$$

$$p'_{(0,n)}(t) = -[(N-n)\lambda + n\mu_n]p_{(0,n)}(t) + (N-n+1)\lambda p_{(0,n-1)}(t) + (n+1)\mu_{n+1}p_{(0,n+1)}(t) + \theta q_{(0,n)}(t); \quad 2 \leq n \leq M-1 \tag{4.3}$$

$$p'_{(0,M)}(t) = -[(N-M)\lambda + M\mu_M]p_{(0,M)}(t) + (N-M+1)\lambda p_{(0,M-1)}(t) + M\mu_M p_{(1,M)}(t) + \theta q_{(0,M)}(t) \tag{4.4}$$

$$p'_{(n,M)}(t) = -[(N-M-n)\lambda + M\mu_M]p_{(n,M)}(t) + (N-M-n+1)\lambda p_{(n-1,M)}(t) + M\mu_M p_{(n+1,M)}(t) + \theta q_{(n,M)}(t); \quad 1 \leq n \leq L-1 \tag{4.5}$$

$$p'_{(L,M)}(t) = -M\mu_M p_{(N-M,M)}(t) + \lambda p_{(N-M-1,M)}(t) + \theta q_{(N-M,M)}(t) \tag{4.6}$$

$$q'_{(0,n)}(t) = -[(N-n)\lambda + \theta]q_{(0,n)}(t) + (N-n+1)\lambda q_{(0,n-1)}(t); \quad 1 \leq n \leq M \tag{4.7}$$

$$q'_{(n,M)}(t) = -[(N-(M+n))\lambda + \theta]q_{(n,M)}(t) + (N-(M+n-1))\lambda q_{(n-1,M)}(t); \quad 1 \leq n \leq L-1 \tag{4.8}$$

$$q'_{(L,M)}(t) = -\theta q_{(L,M)}(t) + (N-(M+L-1))\lambda q_{(L-1,M)}(t) \tag{4.9}$$

The corresponding matrix form for equations (4.1) to (4.9) is,

$$p'(t) = Ap(t) \tag{4.10}$$

where,

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} D_0 & B_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ D_1 & A_1 & B_2 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & C_1 & A_2 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C_2 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & A_{M-1} & B_M & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & C_{M-1} & A_M & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & A_{M+(L-1)} & B_{M+L} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & C_{M+(L-1)} & A_{M+L} \end{bmatrix}$$

and the submatrices are

$$D_0 = [-N\lambda], D_1 = \begin{bmatrix} N\lambda \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, B_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \mu_1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$B_i = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & i\mu_i \end{bmatrix}; \quad 2 \leq i \leq M$$

$$B_{M+i} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & M\mu_M \end{bmatrix}; \quad 1 \leq i \leq L$$

$$C_i = \begin{bmatrix} (N-i)\lambda & 0 \\ 0 & (N-i)\lambda \end{bmatrix}; \quad 1 \leq i \leq M$$

$$C_{M+i} = \begin{bmatrix} (N-(M+i)\lambda & 0 \\ 0 & (N-(M+i)\lambda) \end{bmatrix}; \quad 1 \leq i \leq L-1$$

$$A_i = \begin{bmatrix} -[(N-i)\lambda + \theta] & 0 \\ \theta & -[(N-i)\lambda + i\mu_i] \end{bmatrix}; \quad 1 \leq i \leq M$$

$$A_{M+i} = \begin{bmatrix} -[(N-(M+i))\lambda + \theta] & 0 \\ \theta & -[(N-(M+i))\lambda + M\mu_M] \end{bmatrix}; \quad 1 \leq i \leq L$$

The probability vector is,

$$p(t) = (p_0(t), p_1(t), \dots, p_{M-1}(t), p_M(t), p_{M+1}(t), \dots, p_{M+(N-M-1)}(t), p_{M+(N-M)}(t))^T \quad (4.11)$$

where,

$$p_0(t) = (q_{(0,0)}(t))$$

$$p_i(t) = (q_{(0,i)}(t), p_{(0,i)}(t)); \quad 1 \leq i \leq M$$

$$p_{M+i}(t) = (q_{(i,M)}(t), p_{(i,M)}(t)); \quad 1 \leq i \leq L$$

Integrating the equation (4.10), we get,

$$p(t) = e^{At} \cdot C \quad (4.12)$$

$$\text{At } t=0, C=p(0) \quad (4.13)$$

$$\text{The solution vector at time } t \text{ is, } p(t) = p(0) \cdot e^{At} \quad (4.14)$$

where $p(0)$ is the initial probability vector.

The exponential of the matrix can be computed in many ways (Moler and Loan (2003)). The methods can be obtained from classical results in analysis, approximation theory and matrix theory. One of the methods is the series method. An algorithm is developed, the definition $e^{At} = I + At + \frac{(At)^2}{2!} + \dots$ is the basis for the algorithm. The series is summed until adding another term does not alter the recent number stored in the computer. Then the resulting value is taken as e^{At} . The probability vector $p(t)$ in (4.14) is obtained by assuming the initial probability vector $p(0) = [1, 0, 0, \dots, 0]^T$.

4.2 Some Performance Measures

By straight forward calculation, the following performances are obtained.

1. Mean number of customers in the queue at time t

$$L_1(t) = \sum_{n=0}^L n [q_{(n,M)}(t) + p_{(n,M)}(t)] \quad (4.15)$$

2. Mean number of customers in the system at time t

$$L_2(t) = \sum_{n=0}^M n [q_{(0,n)}(t) + p_{(0,n)}(t)] + \sum_{n=0}^L n [q_{(n,M)}(t) + p_{(n,M)}(t)] \quad (4.16)$$

3. Second moment of Mean number of customers in the system at time t

$$L_3(t) = \sum_{n=0}^M n^2 [q_{(0,n)}(t) + p_{(0,n)}(t)] + \sum_{n=0}^L n^2 [q_{(n,M)}(t) + p_{(n,M)}(t)] \quad (4.17)$$

4. Mean number of customers in the service station at time t

$$L_4(t) = \sum_{n=0}^M n [p_{(0,n)}(t) + q_{(0,n)}(t)] + M \sum_{n=1}^L [p_{(n,M)}(t) + q_{(n,M)}(t)] \quad (4.18)$$

5. Mean number of customers in the source at time t

$$L_5(t) = \sum_{n=0}^M (N - n) [q_{(0,n)}(t) + p_{(0,n)}(t)] + \sum_{n=1}^L (L - n) [q_{(n,M)}(t) + p_{(n,M)}(t)] \tag{4.19}$$

6. Mean number of customers in the queue when the server is on vacation at time t

$$L_6(t) = \sum_{n=0}^M nq_{(0,n)}(t) + \sum_{n=0}^L nq_{(n,M)}(t) \tag{4.20}$$

7. Mean number of customers in the system when the server is busy

$$L_7(t) = \sum_{n=0}^M np_{(0,n)}(t) + \sum_{n=1}^L (n + M)p_{(n,M)}(t) \tag{4.21}$$

5 A Comparative Case Study

In this section, the performance measures which are given in subsection 3.2 and 4.2 are calculated numerically by assuming particular values to the parameters $N(20)$, $M(8)$, $L(11)$ and $\mu_1(1)$, $\mu_2(1.1)$, $\mu_3(1.2)$, $\mu_4(1.3)$, $\mu_5(1.4)$, $\mu_6(1.5)$, $\mu_7(1.6)$, $\mu_8(1.7)$ and $\lambda(0.1 - 1)$, $\theta(0.1)$, $t(12,24,36,48,60)$. The calculated values are given in table 5.1. Also, graphs are shown in Figure 5.2, Figure 5.3 and Figure 5.4.

Table 5.1: Comparative Analysis of Model I and Model II

Mean Value	λ	12hrs		36hrs		60hrs	
		Model I	Model II	Model I	Model II	Model I	Model II
Mean number of customers in the system at time t	0.1	4.1387	4.1385	4.6421	4.6091	4.6435	4.6082
	0.3	6.4992	6.3085	5.3798	5.2639	5.3560	5.2442
	0.5	7.1391	6.8292	5.3974	5.3319	5.2783	5.2303
	0.7	7.3187	6.9987	5.47014	5.43091	5.3122	5.2970
	0.9	7.1714	6.8508	5.2094	5.1777	5.0338	5.0279

Figure: 5.2: Curve $L_2(t)$ for $\lambda = 0.1$

Figure: 5.3: Curve $L_2(t)$ for $\lambda = 0.5$

From the figures 5.2, 5.3 and 5.4, it is clear that the mean number of customers in the system with respect to t increases for both the models at $\lambda = 0.1$. Whereas for $\lambda = 0.5$ and $\lambda = 0.9$, the mean values decrease with respect to the time t (0 to 60 time units). As a comparison, the mean value of Model I is slightly higher than the mean value of Model II for $\lambda = 0.1, 0.5$ and 0.9 .

Figure: 5.4: Curve $L_2(t)$ for $\lambda = 0.9$

6 Control Chart Analysis

The models are statistically analyzed by studying control chart analysis for mean number customers in the system at time t . The control limit (CL), the upper control limit (UCL) and the lower control limit (LCL) are obtained using the following formulas

$CL = L_2(t)$, $UCL = L_2(t) + 3\sqrt{\text{Variance}}$ and $LCL = L_2(t) - 3\sqrt{\text{Variance}}$ LCL for various values of λ and t the results are shown in tables 6.1 and 6.5. Also, the graphs are drawn and are given in the Figures 6.2, 6.3, 6.4, 6.6, 6.7 and 6.8. From the figure it is clear that our calculated values (CLV) almost nearer to the CL values.

Table 6.1: The control chart table for Model I

Control values	λ	12 hrs	36 hrs	60 hrs
LCL	0.1	-3.26844 \approx 0	-4.9458 \approx 0	-4.9568 \approx 0
	0.5	-3.6617 \approx 0	-2.1019 \approx 0	-1.7964 \approx 0
	0.9	-4.1424 \approx 0	-2.5851 \approx 0	-2.1326 \approx 0
CL	0.1	4.1387	4.6421	4.6434
	0.5	7.1391	5.3974	5.2783
	0.9	7.1714	5.2094	5.0338
UCL	0.1	11.5459	14.2301	14.2438
	0.5	17.9400	12.8967	12.3531
	0.9	18.4853	13.0038	12.2001

Figure: 6.2: Control chart for $\lambda = 0.1$

Figure: 6.3: Control chart for $\lambda = 0.5$

Figure: 6.4: Control chart for $\lambda = 0.9$

Table 6.5: The control chart table for Model II

Control values	λ	12hrs	36hrs	60hrs
LCL	0.1	-3.2665 ≈ 0	-4.7705 ≈ 0	-4.7685 ≈ 0
	0.5	-2.7853 ≈ 0	-1.6815 ≈ 0	-1.4621 ≈ 0
	0.9	-3.30578 ≈ 0	-2.3892 ≈ 0	-2.0920 ≈ 0
CL	0.1	4.1385	4.6091	4.6082
	0.5	6.8292	5.3319	5.2303
	0.9	6.8508	5.1776	5.0279
UCL	0.1	11.5434	13.9886	13.9848
	0.5	16.4438	12.3454	11.9227
	0.9	17.0074	12.7445	12.1478

Figure: 6.6: Control chart for $\lambda = 0.1$

Figure: 6.7: Control chart for $\lambda = 0.5$

Figure: 6.8: Control chart for $\lambda = 0.9$

7 Conclusion

This paper deals with a single server finite source various batch service queue. The maximum size of service batch is assumed as M . Also, the batch is accessible batch. After completion of service, the servers in the batch leaves singly. The server applied multiple vacation policy. Two models namely, delay model and loss model are analyzed in time dependent domain. Control chart analysis is also carried out. Some numerical illustrations are also provided. The model can be generalized by assuming general service time distribution.

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